

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

MOLECULAR CHARACTERISTICS, THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAFT COPOLYMERS OF CELLULOSE AND TEXTILE FABRICS

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Abstract

The molecular characteristics of graft copolymers of cellulose with acrylic polymers have been obtained and determined. The thermal properties of graft copolymers of cellulose with polyacrylic acid were determined by differential scanning calorimetry. Intense weight loss of copolymers is shifted to the high-temperature region, the value of the exothermic effect of thermal-oxidative decomposition increases in comparison with the cellulose cyst. Cotton textile fabrics with grafted synthetic polymers were obtained, the dependences of the tensile strength, density, and air permeability of the material on the nature and degree of grafting of the synthetic polymer were determined.

Keywords: cellulose, acrylic monomer, grafting, textile material.

Introduction

Graft copolymerization, as a way to change the properties of natural polymers, has been successfully used by researchers for a long time [1–12]. To obtain graft copolymers of natural polymers with functionally active monomers, redox systems are used: potassium persulfate [13], tetravalent cerium ions [14], benzoyl peroxide [15], trivalent cobalt complex ion [16], benzophenone as a photoinitiator [17] and other redox systems.

The properties of natural and chemical fibers complement each other, which makes it possible to obtain high-quality products from their mixtures. However, along with the advantages, natural, especially cellulose, fibers have some disadvantages - increased fire hazard, replacement, premature destruction of fibers under operating conditions, etc. The grafting of synthetic polymers, flame retardants, hydrophobic-hydrophilic fillers on the surface of traditional textile materials contributes to the purposeful modification of their properties. The greatest positive effect is achieved with the chemical fixation of modifying compositions with textile material.

Heating processes and thermal decomposition products are important properties, especially for fire-resistant materials. The purpose of this work is to determine the thermal stability of graft copolymers of cellulose with acrylic monomers, to determine some of the mechanical properties of textile fabrics with graft copolymers.

Experimental part

The synthesis of the graft copolymer was carried out in a three-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, a thermometer, and a reflux condenser in a nitrogen flow

[18, 19]. Acrylic acid (AA), cellulose fibers, potassium persulfate (PP) as an initiator and water were loaded into the flask. The flask was immersed in a thermostat with a certain temperature. Synthesis of copolymers was carried out with constant stirring of the reaction mass in a heterogeneous mixture. Upon reaching a certain time, the reaction mixture was removed from the thermostat and cooled to room temperature. Unreacted monomer and ungrafted polyacrylic acid are separated from the graft copolymer by extraction in ethanol. The resulting copolymer was placed in a desiccator connected to a vacuum pump and dried to constant weight.

To obtain a textile material based on cotton (cotton) fabric, a thoroughly washed and dried fabric was kept in an aqueous solution of PA, passing nitrogen through the solution. The fabric was removed from the solution and dried at room temperature. Grafting of monomers - acrylic acid (AA), methyl methacrylate (MMA), n-butyl methacrylate (BMA), acrylonitrile (AN) was carried out. In a three-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, a reflux condenser, and an inert gas inlet tube, the solvent, fabric, and monomer were placed. By passing nitrogen gas through the reaction mixture, the flask was heated in a water bath with occasional stirring at 60°C for 4 hours. The amount of monomer was 10–25% by weight of the fabric, the amount of initiator was 1–2% by weight of the monomer. After the completion of the process, the fabric was removed from the solution, washed several times in a polymer solvent, and dried to constant weight in an oven. Based on the results of measuring the mass of the web before and after polymerization, taking into account the mass of the monomer and initiator, the degree and efficiency of

grafting the synthetic polymer on cellulose fibers [20] and cotton fabrics were calculated.

The thermal properties of cellulose copolymers with polyacrylic acid (PAA) were studied using the method of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Thermoanalytical studies of copolymers were carried out on a Netzsch Simultaneous Analyzer 409 PG (Germany), with a K-type thermocouple (Low RG Silver) and aluminum crucibles. All measurements were carried out in an inert nitrogen atmosphere with a nitrogen flow rate of 50 ml/min. The temperature range of measurements was 0-560°C, the heating rate was 10⁰/min. The amount of sample per measurement is 20-30 mg. The measuring system was calibrated with a standard set of substances KNO₃, In, Bi, Sn, Zn, CsCl.

The tensile strength and air permeability of the fabrics were determined at the "CENTEXUZ" certifi-

cation center. The discontinuous characteristic of materials was determined on the "AO-1" dynamometer (tensile testing machine). The device works together with a computer according to a special program, the maximum breaking force of the device is 1000 N. The test results are printed on the printer in the form of a graph and a table. The air conductivity of the material was determined using the device for determining the air permeability "AP-36 OSM", sample dimensions 160x160 mm.

Results and its discussion

Changes in the molecular characteristics of cellulose graft copolymers with a change in the concentration of components corresponding to the regularities of radical polymerization. An increase in the concentration of the initiator leads to an increase in the degree of grafting, a slight increase in the efficiency of grafting, a significant decrease in the degree of polymerization and molecular weight of grafted chains (Table 1).

Table 1
Dependence of the degree and efficiency of grafting monomers to cellulose and the average molecular weight of grafted chains on the concentration of potassium persulfate.

T=60°C, time – 4 hours

Monomer and its concentration, mol/l	PA concentration, mol/l·10 ²	Degree of conversion, %	Degree of grafting, %	Effectiveness of grafting, %	Average degree of polymerization	Average MM of grafted chains
AA, 1,39	0,37	52,4	13,4	25,5	98	7000
	0,74	75,3	18,7	24,8	71	5100
	1,11	88,6	23,0	26,0	55	4000
MMA, 1,0	0,37	49,8	8,8	17,7	67	6700
	0,74	69,5	15,3	22,0	47	4700
	1,11	83,7	21,4	25,6	38	3800

In a heterogeneous process, an increase in the efficiency of grafting with an increase in the concentration of the initiator is promoted by the additional adsorption interaction of the initiator molecules with the cellulose surface.

As expected, the monomer concentration does not affect the degree of conversion and the grafting efficiency, but significantly affects the molecular weight of the grafted chains (Table 2).

Table 2
Dependence of the degree and efficiency of grafting of monomers to cellulose and the average molecular weight of grafted chains on the concentration of monomers.

[PA]=0,74·10⁻² mol/l, T=60°C, time – 4 hour

Monomer	Concentration of monomer, mol/l	Degree of conversion, %	Degree of grafting, %	Effectiveness of grafting, %	Average degree of polymerization	Average MM of grafted chains
AA	0,69	76,2	10,1	26,5	36	2600
	1,39	75,3	18,7	24,8	71	5100
	2,08	78,7	24,5	20,8	112	8100
MMA	0,5	67,4	9,2	27,3	23	2300
	1,0	69,5	15,3	22,0	47	4700
	1,5	68,9	22,7	21,9	70	7000

With an increase in the concentration of monomers, the total degree of conversion slightly increases, the efficiency of grafting decreases slightly, and the degree of grafting, the degree of polymerization, and the molecular weight of grafted chains increase significantly. Apparently, the overall degree of conversion depends mainly on the concentration of the initiator, and not the monomer. At the same concentration of the initiator, the number of active centers initiating graft copolymerization does not change, and with an increase

in the concentration of monomers, the number of molecules attached to each active center increases. Naturally, this leads to a proportional increase in the degree of polymerization and the molecular weight of the grafted chains.

The structure of copolymers largely depends on the concentration of the initiator. At sufficiently high degrees of conversion, with an increase in the concentration of the initiator, the proportion of the gel fraction of the polymer increases. Of course, with an increase in

the molecular weight of the grafted chains, which occurs with an increase in the monomer concentration, the probability of recombination of growing chains with subsequent formation of a network structure increases. But the length of the side chains was not sufficient to form a fully networked structure. The network frequency, which depends on the concentration of active

sites of initiation, turned out to be decisive for the ratio of the sol-gel fractions of the obtained graft copolymers.

When heated, cotton cellulose begins to lose weight after 50°C, by 150°C the weight loss is approximately 10% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. DSC analysis of cotton cellulose.

This loss is associated with the volatilization of adsorbed water. With further heating, the decrease in mass continues and by 350°C is 40%. In the range of 390-480°C, intense weight loss is accompanied by an exothermic deviation with a maximum at 426°C. In this temperature range, the processes of crosslinking and

cyclization occur with the release of low molecular weight products, the thermal effect of which is $\Delta H=700$ J/g. The total weight loss up to 560°C is 72%.

Consider the results of the DSC analysis of the copolymer of cotton cellulose and PAA (Figure 2).

Figure 2. DSC analysis of a copolymer of cotton cellulose and PAA.

Judging by the thermogravimetry (TG) curve, the copolymer of cellulose and PAA turned out to be thermally stable up to a temperature of 280°C, after which an intense weight loss begins, accompanied by an exothermic effect. After 340°C, the weight loss slows down somewhat, then continues with less intensity. In contrast to pure cellulose, there are two maxima on the DSC curve. The first at 359°C, and the second at 485°C. The first peak in cotton cellulose was not found. A chemical reaction occurs in the copolymer between the carboxyl groups of PAA and the hydroxyl groups of cellulose with the formation of a crosslink, condensation of water, and release of heat. The second maximum corresponds to the processes of chemical interaction in the cellulose itself, also with the formation of a cross-linked structure. At the maximum point, the temperature value is higher than for cellulose. The total weight loss at 560°C is 98%.

The principles of forming film and fire-resistant materials based on a collagen-polyacrylic composition [21–23] were used to produce cotton fabrics with grafted synthetic polymers.

The degree of grafting of monomers to the textile fabric turned out to be less than to similar fibers. On the

other hand, the content of synthetic polymer in the range of 4–6% by weight of the base will have a rather significant effect on the properties of the material. Under the same conditions, the degree of grafting depends on the nature of the monomer; the activity of monomers in copolymerization reactions decreases in the series AA>MMA>BMA>AN.

Some physical and mechanical properties of the obtained textile materials were determined (Figure 3). As can be seen from the data in Figure 3, the tensile strength of the copolymers is higher than that of the fabric itself. Cotton + PAA material has the highest strength, apparently, with an increase in the degree of grafting, the mechanical strength also increases. As in the case of a material based on collagen [21, 22], with an increase in the geometric dimensions of the grafted monomer molecule, the elongation in tension increases. The PBMA material is stretched by about 20%, which is 1.5–2.0 times more than the untreated material and the material with PAA and PMMA. By changing the nature and geometric dimensions of the monomer, it is possible to control the elastic-strength properties of the fabrics.

Figure 3. Dependence of the tensile strength of cotton textile fabrics on the relative elongation. 1.2. cotton canvas, 3.0 cotton + PMMA, 5.8. cotton + PAN, 7.0 cotton + PAK, 4.6. cotton + PBMA.

The air conductivity and surface density of the fabrics change significantly with the content of small amounts of synthetic polymers (Table 3). As can be seen from the table, with an increase in the degree of grafting, the surface density increases proportionally,

and the air conductivity decreases disproportionately with the degree of grafting. If the surface density depends only on the degree of grafting, then the air conductivity of the material depends on both the degree of grafting and the nature of the copolymer.

Table 3

Dependence of air conductivity and surface density of textile fabrics on the nature of the graft copolymer

Material	Air conduction cm ³ /cm ² ·cec at 20°C, 1atm.	Surface density, g/m ²
Textile base cotton	253,1	110,4
cotton + PAA	155,2	144,4
cotton + PBMA	155,6	132,0
cotton + PMAA	147,7	139,5
cotton + PAN	158,5	126,0

The dimensions of the side chains of monomers and the parameters of the networks of graft copolymers determine the permeability of the flow of air and water through the pores of the material. Naturally, with an increase in the geometric dimensions of the side chains of monomers and the density of cross-links, these indicators decrease. Hence the non-proportionality of the change in air conductivity with the degree of grafting and with the surface density.

Conclusions

The physicochemical and mechanical properties of graft copolymers of natural polymers with functionally active monomers depend on the composition, structure, and preparation conditions. Thermal stability is determined by the degree of conversion, cross-linking of the base polymer with macromolecules of the grafted polymer. With an increase in the degree of grafting and, accordingly, the frequency of cross-linked networks, the density and thermal stability of the copolymer increase. In copolymers of natural polymers with polyacrylates, an insignificant endothermic process is observed, indicating partial melting of the sample. At higher temperatures, an intense weight loss of copolymers occurs, accompanied by an exothermic peak in the DSC curve, as a result of crosslinking and cyclization reactions with the release of low molecular weight products. The results obtained confirm the mesh structure of cellulose graft copolymers with functionally active monomers.

The thickness and surface density of all materials naturally and proportionally increase with an increase in the degree of grafting of the synthetic polymer. In the compositions "cotton fabric - synthetic polymer" strength increases, air conductivity decreases. This is facilitated by the compaction of the material and the formation of a mesh structure as a result of the graft copolymerization of a natural polymer with monomers.

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